

Connecting floras and herbaria before 1850 – challenges and lessons learned in digital history of biodiversity

SESSION 3B

AUTHORS

Christian Forney [✉](#) [ORCID](#) [external link](#)

Martin Stuber [✉](#) [ORCID](#) [external link](#)

AFFILIATION

University of Bern

University of Bern

PUBLISHED

August 8, 2024

MODIFIED

September 17, 2024

DOI

[10.5281/zenodo.13768615](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13768615) [external link](#)

ABSTRACT

Floras and herbaria are particularly valuable sources both for historical analyses of the collaborative knowledge culture of botany and for research into historical biodiversity. Therefore, the digital representation of this complementary sources should fulfil the requirements of the humanities and natural sciences as well. In this paper, we describe challenges, solutions and lessons learned in this regard as a summary of experiences from multiple projects on the data and edition platform *hallerNet* around the Bernese polymath Albrecht von Haller (1708–1777).

KEYWORDS

Biodiversity, Botanical networks, Digital edition, Digital herbaria, Digital humanities, FAIR data, History of botany, Knowledge history

Introduction

To start with some definitions, the term “flora” – in the sense of a document – denotes a directory in which the plant species of a specific area are systematically listed, often together with a description and additional information. “Herbarium” refers to a collection of preserved (usually dried and pressed) plants or fungi for scientific purposes; an individual botanical object in a herbarium collected at a specific place and time is called a “specimen” (Wagenitz 2003).

Floras and herbaria in the history of knowledge

Both the flora and the herbarium are regarded as decisive innovations in the development of botany into an independent scientific discipline from the mid-16th century onwards. Together with the botanical garden, which is functionally related and established in the same period (Rieppel 2016; Findlen 2006a), only the invention of the herbarium made it possible to work out regional floras based on systematic empirical fieldwork (Flannery 2023; Müller-Wille 2019). Paula Findlen summarised the motivation behind this crucial invention: “The more naturalists observed nature in situ, the more they realized that limited contact with specimens did not yet yield enough knowledge to describe and compare medicinal herbs. They needed to take nature home” (Findlen 2006b, 447; see Sunderland 2016). Findlen stands for the history of knowledge or the renewed history of science that firstly emphasises the shift from finalised knowledge to the act of its production, secondly shows an increased interest in the everyday intellectual life of small groups, circles or networks and thirdly focuses on practices and material cultures of knowledge (Müller-Wille, Carsten, and Sommer 2017; Förschler and Mariss 2017; Holenstein, Steinke, and Stuber 2013). In this perspective and with the catchy phrase “collecting as knowledge”, the creation of a natural history collection, such as a herbarium, is seen as knowledge production (Heesen and Spary 2001). The activity of collecting expresses not only the fact that dispersed natural objects are brought together in a single location, but also that the forms of representation associated with them, such as illustrations, descriptions, lists and publications, are included in the repositories, where they are available for comparison, retracing and synoptic synthesis (Klemun 2017, 235).

The precise structures and functions of floras and herbaria with their spatial relations between local and global can only be understood in the context of the “collaborative knowledge culture of botany”. Therefore the interplay of the three central resources on which botany depended in early modern times has to be reconstructed: living and dried plants, relevant specialised literature (e.g. floras) and correspondence (Dietz 2017a, 2017b). The nexus of correspondence, plant transfer and collection policy was first reconstructed by Emma Spary using the example of the network of André Thouin (1747–1824), director of the *Jardin du Roi* in Paris (Spary 2000, 49–98). The analysis of such networks draws attention to the extensive transfer of dried plants and seeds as the basis of knowledge production (Dauser et al. 2008). A wide variety of methods has been used to correspond efficiently, to save time and to avoid loss of information. First and foremost is the use of reference catalogues. This means that lists of transmitted or desired plant species could simply be referred to the numbers that had been assigned to the species in an

published flora ([Dietz 2017a, 96–99](#)). Secondly, network analyses show that natural history owes its existence not only to the outstanding figures, but also developed through the participation of thousands of amateurs working locally ([Klemun 2017, 239](#)). Correspondence networks not only serve to improve understanding of herbaria and floras, it is also possible to go in the opposite direction: herbaria themselves can serve as a source for social network analyses by systematically evaluating the collectors of the individual specimen ([Siracusa et al. 2020](#); [Groom, O’Reilly, and Humphrey 2014](#)).

Digitisation of herbaria from a botanical perspective

The value of herbaria has long been recognized in the fields of taxonomy, systematics and biogeography. Moreover, in recent decades they have proven to be fundamental for dealing with the biology of climate change, biodiversity, phenology, conservation and biological invasions. Given the high scientific and cultural value of herbarium collections, many efforts to make them more accessible have already been made in the last 20 years. Digitization is an essential first step in the process of transforming this vast amount of data associated with physical specimen into flexible digital data formats that allow information to be re-categorized according to variable criteria ([Roma-Marzio et al. 2023, 108](#); see generally [Andraschke and Wagner 2020](#)). Building on centuries of research based on herbarium specimens collected over time and around the globe, which are freely accessible and aggregable, a “new era” of discovery, synthesis and prediction using digitized collection data is postulated ([James et al. 2018](#); [Nelson and Ellis 2018](#)). Digitization and online availability of specimen facilitates the rapid exploration and dissemination of accurate biodiversity data on an unprecedented scale: “The emerging ‘herbarium of the future’ (or the ‘global metaherbarium’) will be the central element guiding the exploration, illumination, and prediction of plant biodiversity change in the Anthropocene” ([Davis 2023, 412](#)). It should be borne in mind that collections are usually associated with various distortions that need to be characterised and mitigated to make data usable. Most common are taxonomic and collector biases, which can be understood as the effects of particular recording preferences of key collectors on the overall taxonomic composition of the biological collections to which they contribute ([Siracusa et al. 2020](#); [Davis 2023, 421](#); [Jaroszynska et al. 2023](#)). In order to capture such phenomena so that they can be taken into account in the data analysis, precise knowledge of the entire context in which a herbarium was created is required. This is exactly the aim of the approach described above under history of knowledge. Obviously, there is a bridge here between the research interests of the natural sciences and the humanities. An overview published in 2024 shows that the topic of accessibility and digitization of herbaria as “archives of biodiversity” has also gained new relevance in Switzerland in recent years. Apart from two major exceptions, the [Platter-Herbarium](#) [↗](#) and [Les Herbiers de Rousseau](#) [↗](#), there have been no attempts to do this in an interdisciplinary context ([Stämpfli 2024](#)). Additionally there is a lack of including the interaction with the functionally linked correspondence networks and contemporary floras. For this reason, the experience with historical plants gained on *hallerNet*, on which we pursued an interdisciplinary approach to the interaction between different types of entities (letters, species, specimens, reviews), may be of general interest.

Historical plants on the data and edition platform *hallerNet*

The data and edition platform [hallerNet](#) opens up historical networks of knowledge in Switzerland in their interconnectedness. The platform is institutionally supported by the *Albrecht von Haller Foundation of the Burgergemeinde Bern* and the Historical Institute and the Institute for the History of Medicine at the University of Bern. The basis of the currently around 128,000 data objects is formed by extensive prosopographical and bibliographical data that has been compiled in a relational database (FAUST) since the early 1990s as part of three SNSF projects at the University of Bern. A transformation project (2016–2019) transferred this extensively interlinked data into a XML data structure compliant to the [Text Encoding Initiative \(TEI\)](#) and thus turned it into “reusable research data” based on the [FAIR](#) data criteria (Dängeli and Stuber 2020). The platform nowadays contains, among others, around 46,000 publications, 31,000 persons and 1,200 institutions, which are systematically linked to 9,000 edited reviews and 5,000 edited letters. In our context, the 4,955 plant entities currently on *hallerNet* are at the centre. Starting point were the 1,737 species of flowering plants mentioned in Haller’s *Swiss Flora Historia Stirpium* (Haller 1768), which were systematically referenced in the aforementioned relational database to Haller’s first edition of the *Swiss Flora Enumeratio* (Haller 1742), to Linné’s *Species plantarum* (Linné 1753) and to the current nomenclature. This concordance between Haller’s and Linné’s nomenclature, compiled by Luc Lienhard with reference to Johan Rudolf Suter’s *Flora Helvetica* (Suter 1802), not only makes Haller’s Swiss flora accessible, but does also provide access to pre-Linnaean botany in general. On this basis, we transformed the botanical data, which was originally divided into four different data types, for the new XML structure into a generic data model based on today’s plant entities ([InfoFlora](#), [Global Biodiversity Information Facility GBIF](#)), and treat their (historical) names as name variants. In this way, entities become flexibly adaptable for other historical floras that are partly or completely outside Haller’s and Linné’s nomenclature. At the same time, the data model structured according to today’s nomenclature facilitates reference to current issues in historical ecology. The following summary of realized, initiated or planned expansions illustrates this double advantage.

- **Ecological data:** The diverse ecological information in Haller’s *Historia* on habitat, frequency, typical altitudinal range and specific localities is of far above-average quality for the 18th century (Lienhard 2005; Drouin and Lienhard 2008). *hallerNet* systematically records a total of 7,545 locality details, whereby the 1,920 different localities have been georeferenced for the most part as kilometre squares with their corner points and additionally linked to the neighbouring municipalities (‘populated places’) in order to appear in the *hallerNet* place register. Haller’s extraordinary data is thus available in a flexible structure whose exploration is only just beginning (Lienhard 2008, 2000). Historical biodiversity research, which is high on the agenda of environmental history (Goethem and Zanden 2019), has a wealth of source material at its disposal. Using appropriate methods of analysis, this will massively extend its temporal scope beyond the Swiss state of research (Jaroszynska et al. 2023; Wang et al. 2023; Stöckli et al. 2012; Lachat 2010).

- **Collectors and correspondents:** Haller's *Historia* also often includes the collector to whom Haller owes the information. These 109 people are all curated on *hallerNet* and systematically referenced for each species (1,342 times in total). The network is to be further expanded by systematically labelling the plants mentioned in Haller's botanical correspondence, some of which has already been edited on *hallerNet* and most of which are made accessible via the [International Image Interoperability Framework \(IIIF\)](#) . How great the potential of the correspondence is, both for the reconstruction of the 'knowledge culture' and for the supplementation and specification of the location data, is demonstrated by some analyses already available ([Favre 2021](#); [Hächler 2008](#); [Lienhard 2005](#)).
- **Book references and reviews:** For his extensive information on the plant species of his Swiss flora, Haller also uses a vast amount of historical data from his predecessors. For example synonyms and place references, which have already been added to *hallerNet*. Together with the links to Haller's other botanical publications ([Steinke and Profos 2004, 186–95](#)), to the numerous botanical publications in Haller's personal library ([Monti 1983–1994](#), integrated in *hallerNet*) and to Haller's countless botanical reviews in the *Göttingische Gelehrten Anzeigen*, all of which are available in edited form on *hallerNet*, the integral process of botanical knowledge production could be precisely reconstructed (see [Dietz submitted](#); [Lienhard 2005](#); [Drouin and Lienhard 2008](#)).
- **Useful plants:** 656 species or varieties are listed in a total of eleven systematic catalogues in the context of the *Bernese Economic Society*, which was presided over by Haller. In this catalogues, the Latin-universal plant names were consistently linked to the dialectal-regional plant names. On *hallerNet*, 755 actions are linked to them, most of which obtained from the meetings of the *Economic Society* ([Stuber and Lienhard 2007](#); [Stuber 2008](#)). In addition, Haller's Swiss Flora contains information on the medicinal or economic use of more than a quarter of all the flowering plants. This reveals a wide range of interferences with medicine, agriculture, forestry and economy ([Dauser and Stuber submitted](#); [Gerber-Visser and Stuber 2019](#); [Stuber 2018](#); [Boscani Leoni and Stuber 2017](#)).
- **Herbaria:** The digitisation of Haller's herbaria is one of the most intruding unfulfilled postulates in the study of Haller's botany and beyond. Haller's main herbarium, which after being sold by his heirs to Emperor Joseph II was first sent to Pavia and later to Paris by Napoleon, is now in the *Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle* and comprises more than 10,000 specimens in a total of 60 volumes (including 8 volumes of cryptogams) ([Margéz, Aupic, and Lamy 2006](#); [Zoller 1958a](#)); further there is a smaller herbarium by Haller in Göttingen ([Zoller 1958b](#)). Due to the fact that the current location of Haller's herbaria is not in Switzerland, its digitization is not in scope of being supported by the ongoing [SwissCollNet](#) project, the national initiative for the digitization of natural history collections ([Frick, Stieger, and Scheidegger 2019](#)). As part of *SwissCollNet*, however, the lichen herbarium of Jean-Frédéric Chaillet (1747–1839), which is kept in the *Neuchâtel herbarium* (NEU), has now been edited on *hallerNet* as sub-project *Lichens of the Enlightenment* led by Jason Grant. This is consequent in terms of content, as Chaillet operated as a direct Swiss successor to Haller and referred to him wherever possible. At the same time, it represents a milestone for *hallerNet*, as the platform data structures for

Herbaria could be developed. The centrepiece are the 943 lichen specimens, which firstly contain the transcribed original information on the label. Secondly, they are linked to the original scan via [IIIF](#) and additionally with positional accuracy, as there are several specimens stuck on one herbarium page. Thirdly, they are assigned to the species entities, which point to authority data ([GBIF](#), [Index Fungorum](#), [SwissLichens](#)). This species entities also contain the data from historical floras, in this case all from the manuscript flora by Chaillet and, where already listed, from Haller's *Historia*. The information from historical floras is often the decisive key to relate the objects in a herbarium to present-day taxonomic databases. The assignment of source terms to standardised data is thus presented transparently on the platform, which is particularly essential for a period in which botanical nomenclature is still very unstable. Additionally, the structure of the data follows [Darwin Core](#) standard which facilitates the connection to other systems such as the Neuchâtel Herbarium, the emerging *SwissCollNet* database or the global [Index Herbariorum](#) (Vust et al. in prep.).

- **Plant lists:** The connectivity of *hallerNet* is also demonstrated by Meike Knittel's ongoing guest edition of plant lists in the circle of the Zurich botanist Johannes Gessner (1709–1790), the *Naturforschende Gesellschaft* and the botanical garden, which document the actual exchange of seeds and list a total of 1,829 individual actions (see [Knittel in print](#)).

Conclusion

Reconstructing the whole interaction in which floras and herbaria interplayed, difficulties arise in integrating digital approaches to historical correspondence networks (e.g. [Edmondson and Edelstein 2019](#)) with digitization methods for floras and herbaria, which are located in different scientific disciplines. The challenge for the data and edition platform [hallerNet](#) is therefore to find interdisciplinary solutions. With tools, methods and workflows of the digital humanities, traceable relations between text, scans and structural data are determined in an innovative way. That allows to rely today's botanical authority data systematically to the historical information such as changing plant names, specimens, locality information and plant collectors. For the interoperability of the data, the orientation towards the [Darwin Core](#) standard is mandatory, for the sustainable editorial quality the [TEI](#) guidelines. Originally developed in the natural sciences, the [FAIR data principles](#) became a standard in the humanities (especially for *GLAM* institutions), and thus serve as an overarching guideline; in particular, *FAIR* guarantees the sustainable handling of data, which therefore remains 'reusable' for future generations of users because the traces of the normalization and flexibilization processes can be traced in detail. With this integration of different disciplinary standards and different types of sources, *hallerNet* could become a dynamic and cross-collection instrument for the interdisciplinary research of historical plants and biodiversity in Switzerland in the period before 1850. The current transformation of *hallerNet* into the national collaborative platform *République des Lettres*, which began running in 2024 with the support of the *Data Science Lab* of the University of Bern, will further strengthen this potential.

References

- Andraschke, Udo, and Sarah Wagner, eds. 2020. *Objekte im Netz. Wissenschaftliche Sammlungen im digitalen Wandel*. Bielefeld.
- Boscani Leoni, Simona, and Martin Stuber, eds. 2017. *Wer das Gras wachsen hört. Wissensgeschichte(n) der pflanzlichen Ressourcen vom Mittelalter bis ins 20. Jahrhundert*. Jahrbuch für Geschichte des ländlichen Raumes 14.
- Dängeli, Peter, and Martin Stuber. 2020. "Nachhaltigkeit in langjährigen Erschliessungsprojekten. FAIR-Data Kriterien bei Editions- und Forschungsplattformen zum 18. Jahrhundert." *xviii.ch, Schweizerische Zeitschrift für die Erforschung des 18. Jahrhunderts / Revue suisse d'études sur le XVIIIe siècle* 11: 34–51.
<https://doi.org/10.24894/2673-4419.0000410.1515/9783486712339> ↗.
- Dauser, Regina, Stefan Hächler, Michael Kempe, Franz Mauelshagen, and Martin Stuber, eds. 2008. *Wissen im Netz. Botanik und Pflanzentransfer in europäischen Korrespondenznetzen des 18. Jahrhunderts*. Berlin.
- Dauser, Regina, and Martin Stuber. submitted. "Pflanzliche Ressourcen – Interferenzen zwischen Botanik und Ökonomischer Aufklärung." In *Korrespondenz und Kritik. Albrecht von Haller als paradigmatische Figur der entstehenden Scientific Community*, edited by Martin Stuber, Bernhard Metz, and Hubert Steinke. Göttingen.
- Davis, Charles C. 2023. "The Herbarium of the Future." *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 38 (5): 412–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2022.11.015> ↗.
- Dietz, Bettina. submitted. "Orte der Kritik in der Botanik des 18. Jahrhunderts." In *Korrespondenz und Kritik. Albrecht von Haller als paradigmatische Figur der entstehenden Scientific Community*, edited by Martin Stuber, Bernhard Metz, and Hubert Steinke. Göttingen.
- . 2017a. *Das System der Natur. Die kollaborative Wissenskultur der Botanik im 18. Jahrhundert*. Köln u.a.
- . 2017b. "Kollaboration in der Botanik des 18. Jahrhunderts. Die partizipative Architektur von Linnés System der Natur." In *Verfahrensweisen der Naturgeschichte in der Frühen Neuzeit. Akteure Tiere Dinge*, edited by Silke Förschler and Anne Mariss, 93–108. Köln.
- Drouin, Jean-Marc, and Luc Lienhard. 2008. "Botanik." In *Albrecht von Haller. Leben, Werk, Epoche*, edited by Hubert Steinke, Urs Boschung, and Wolfgang Pross, 292–314. Göttingen.
- Edmondson, Chloe, and Dan Edelstein, eds. 2019. *Networks of Enlightenment. Digital Approaches to the Republic of Letters*. Oxford.
- Favre, Madline. 2021. "Réseaux, pratiques et motivations des acteurs locaux de la recherche botanique en milieu alpin. Le cas du Valais entre 1750 et 1810." In *Histoire naturelle et montagnes – Storia naturale e montagna – Naturgeschichte und Berge*, edited by Simona Boscani Leoni, Anne-Lise Head, and Luigi Lorenzetti, 32–49. *Histoire des Alpes / Storia delle Alpi / Geschichte der Alpen* 26.
- Findlen, Paula. 2006a. "Anatomy Theaters, Botanical Gardens, and Natural History Collections." In *Early Modern Science*, edited by Katharina Park and Lorraine Daston,

- 272–89. *The Cambridge History of Science* 3. Cambridge.
- . 2006b. "Natural History." In *Early Modern Science*, edited by Katharina Park and Lorraine Daston, 435–68. *The Cambridge History of Science* 3. Cambridge.
- Flannery, Maura C. 2023. *In the Herbarium: The Hidden World of Collecting and Preserving Plants*. New Haven.
- Förschler, Silke, and Anne Mariss, eds. 2017. *Akteure, Tiere, Dinge : Verfahrensweisen der Naturgeschichte in der Frühen Neuzeit*. Köln.
- Frick, Holger, Pia Stieger, and Christoph Scheidegger. 2019. "SwissCollNet – a National Initiative for Natural History Collections in Switzerland." *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 3: e37188. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.3.37188> .
- Gerber-Visser, Gerrendina, and Martin Stuber. 2019. "Naturgeschichte Helvetiens als Projekt der Ökonomischen Aufklärung. Jakob Samuel Wyttenbachs Forschungsbericht (1788) und Albrecht Höpfners Magazin (1787-1789)." In *Politische, gelehrte und imaginierte Schweiz. Kohäsion und Disparität im Corpus helveticum des 18. Jahrhunderts*, edited by André Holenstein, Claire Jaquier, Timothée Lécho, and Daniel Schläppi, 225–52. Genève.
- Goethem, Thomas van, and Jan Luiten van Zanden. 2019. "Who Is Afraid of Biodiversity? Proposal for a Research Agenda for Environmental History." *Environment and History* 25: 613–47. <https://doi.org/10.3197/096734018X15254461646440> .
- Groom, Quentin, C. O'Reilly, and T. Humphrey. 2014. "Herbarium Specimens Reveal the Exchange Network of British and Irish Botanists, 1856–1932." *New Journal of Botany* 4, 2: 95–103. <https://doi.org/10.1179/2042349714Y.0000000041> .
- Hächler, Stefan. 2008. "Avec une grosse boete de plantes vertes. Pflanzentransfer in der Korrespondenz Albrecht von Hallers (1708-1777)." In *Wissen im Netz. Botanik und Pflanzentransfer in europäischen Korrespondenznetzen des 18. Jahrhunderts*, edited by Regina Dauser, Stefan Hächler, Michael Kempe, Franz Mauelshagen, and Martin Stuber, 201–18. Berlin.
- Haller, Albrecht von. 1742. *Enumeratio methodica stirpium Helvetiae indigenarum*. Gottingae: ex officina academica Abrami Vandenhoeck.
- . 1768. *Historia stirpium indigenarum Helvetiae inchoata*. Bernae: sumptibus Societatis typographicae.
- Heesen, Anke te, and Emma C. Spary, eds. 2001. *Sammeln als Wissen*. Göttingen.
- Holenstein, André, Hubert Steinke, and Martin Stuber, eds. 2013. *Scholars in Action. The Practice of Knowledge and the Figure of the Savant in the 18th Century*. 2 vols. Leiden; Boston.
- James, Shelley A, PS. Soltis, L. Belbin, AD. Chapman, G. Nelson, DL. Paul, and M. Collins. 2018. "Herbarium Data: Global Biodiversity and Societal Botanical Needs for Novel Research." *Applications in Plant Sciences* 6, 2: e1024. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aps3.1024> .
- Jaroszynska, Francesca, Christian Rixen, Sarah Woodin, Jonathan Lenoir, and Sonja Wipf. 2023. "Resampling Alpine Herbarium Records Reveals Changes in Plant Traits over Space and Time." *Journal of Ecology* 111 (2): 338–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.14062> .

- Klemun, Marianne. 2017. "Gärten und Sammlungen." In *Handbuch Wissenschaftsgeschichte*, edited by Marianne Sommer, Staffan Müller-Wille, and Carsten Reinhard, 235–44. Stuttgart.
- Knittel, Meike. in print. *Blühende Beziehungen. Botanische Praktiken im Zürich des 18. Jahrhunderts*.
- Lachat, Thibault, ed. 2010. *Wandel der Biodiversität in der Schweiz seit 1900: ist die Talsohle erreicht?* Bern u.a.
- Lienhard, Luc. 2000. "Haller et la découverte botanique des Alpes." In *Une cordée originale. Histoire des relations entre science et montagne*, edited by Jean-Claude Pont and Jan Lacki, 96–119. Chêne-Bourg.
- . 2005. "La machine botanique. Zur Entstehung von Hallers Flora der Schweiz." In *Hallers Netz. Ein europäischer Gelehrtenbriefwechsel zur Zeit der Aufklärung*, edited by Martin Stuber, Stefan Hächler, and Luc Lienhard, 371–410. Basel.
- . 2008. "Wegränder, Wiesen, Sümpfe – Flora und Lebensräume." In *Berns goldene Zeit. Das 18. Jahrhundert neu entdeckt*, edited by André Holenstein, Daniel Schläppi, Dieter Schnell, Hubert Steinke, Martin Stuber, and Andreas Würigler, 56–59. Bern.
- Linné, Carl von. 1753. *Species plantarum*. Stockholm: Laurentz Salvi.
- Margéz, Marlène, Cécile Aupic, and Denis Lamy. 2006. "La restauration de l'herbier Haller du Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle." *Support tracé* 5: 354–60.
- Monti, Maria Teresa, ed. 1983–1994. *Catalogo del Fondo Haller della Biblioteca Nazionale Braidense di Milano*. 13 vols. Milano.
- Müller-Wille, Staffan. 2019. "Botanik." In *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit Online*. https://doi.org/10.1163/2352-0248_edn_COM_248430 .
- Müller-Wille, Staffan, Reinhardt Carsten, and Marianne Sommer. 2017. "Wissenschaftsgeschichte und Wissensgeschichte." In *Handbuch Wissenschaftsgeschichte*, edited by Marianne Sommer, Staffan Müller-Wille, and Carsten Reinhard, 2–18. Stuttgart.
- Nelson, Gil, and Shari Ellis. 2018. "The History and Impact of Digitization and Digital Data Mobilization on Biodiversity Research." *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 374: 2017039. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2017.0391> .
- Rieppel, Lukas. 2016. "Museums and Botanical Gardens." In *A Companion to the History of Science*, edited by Bernard Lightman, 238–51. Oxford u.a.
- Roma-Marzio, Francesco, S. Maccioni, D. Dolci, G. Astuti, N. Magrini, F. Pierotti, R. Vangelisti, L. Amadei, and L. Peruzzi. 2023. "Digitization of the Historical Herbarium of Michele Guadagno at Pisa (PI-GUAD)." *PhytoKeys* 234: 107–25. <https://doi.org/10.3897/phytokeys.234.109464> .
- Siracusa, Pedro C., Jr. Gadelha, M. R. Luiz, and Arthur Ziviani. 2020. "New Perspectives on Analysing Data from Biological Collections Based on Social Network Analytics." *Sci Rep* 10, 3358. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-60134-y> .
- Spary, Emma. 2000. *Utopias Garden : French Natural History from the Old Regime to Revolution*. London.
- Stämpfli, Remo. 2024. "Pflanzen im Netz: Die Möglichkeiten des Digitalen bei der Erschliessung und Vermittlung von Herbarien und Herbarbelegen." In

Informationswissenschaft: Theorie, Methode Und Praxis, 8 (1):123–44.

<https://doi.org/10.18755/iw.2024.8>

- Steinke, Hubert, and Claudia Profos, eds. 2004. *Bibliographia Halleriana. Verzeichnis der Schriften von und über Albrecht von Haller*. Basel.
- Stöckli, Veronika, S. Wipf, C. Nilsson, and C. Rixen. 2012. "Using Historical Plant Surveys to Track Biodiversity on Mountain Summits Plant." *Ecology and Diversity* 4: 415–25.
- Stuber, Martin. 2008. "Kulturpflanzentransfer im Netz der Oekonomischen Gesellschaft Bern." In *Wissen im Netz. Botanik und Pflanzentransfer in europäischen Korrespondenznetzen des 18. Jahrhunderts*, edited by Regina Dauser, Stefan Hächler, Michael Kempe, Franz Mauelshagen, and Martin Stuber, 229–69. Berlin.
- . 2018. "Vom Simmental bis Spitzbergen. Albrecht von Haller als europäischer Vermittler regionaler Kultur und Ökonomie." In *Zwischen den Kulturen. Mittler und Grenzgänger vom 17. bis 19. Jahrhundert*, edited by Joachim Eibach and Claudia Opitz-Belakhal, 165–89. Hannover.
- Stuber, Martin, and Luc Lienhard. 2007. "Nützliche Pflanzen. Systematische Pflanzenverzeichnisse von Wild- und Kulturpflanzen im Umfeld der Oekonomischen Gesellschaft." In *Nützliche Wissenschaft und Ökonomie im Ancien Régime. Akteure, Themen, Kommunikationsformen*, edited by André Holenstein, Martin Stuber, and Gerrendina Gerber-Visser, 65–106. Cardanus. Jahrbuch für Wissenschaftsgeschichte 7.
- Sunderland, Mary E. 2016. "Specimens and Collections." In *A Companion to the History of Science*, edited by Bernard Lightman, 488–99. Oxford u.a.
- Suter, Johann Rudolf. 1802. *Helvetiens Flora, worinn alle im Hallerischen Werke enthaltenen und seither neu entdeckten Schweizer Pflanzen nach Linné's Methode aufgestellt sind*. 2 Bde. s.l.
- Vust, Mathias, Edouard Di Maio, Christian Forney, and Martin Stuber. in prep. "Les herbiers historiques, défi pour les humanités numériques - l'herbier des lichens de J.-F. Chaillet comme projet pilote." In *Usages, pratiques et fonctions des herbiers historiques*. Actes Colloque Ascona.
- Wagenitz, Gerhard. 2003. *Wörterbuch der Botanik*. 2. Aufl. Heidelberg. Berlin.
- Wang, Jessica, Markus Fischer, Stefan Eggenberg, and Katja Rembold. 2023. "The Impact of Climate Change on Plant Distribution and Niche Dynamics over the Past 250 Years in Switzerland." *Bauhinia* 29: 101–12.
- Zoller, Heinrich. 1958a. "A l'occasion du 250e anniversaire de Albrecht von Haller: quelques remarques sur son oeuvre botanique et ses collections." *Bulletin de Museum national d'histoire naturelle* série 2, t. 30, no 3: 305–12.
- . 1958b. "Albrecht von Hallers Pflanzensammlungen in Göttingen, sein botanisches Werk und sein Verhältnis zu Carl von Linné." *Nachrichten der Akademie der Wissenschaften in Göttingen* 2, Mathematisch-physikalische Klasse, Nr. 10: 217–51.

Reuse

[CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

Citation

BibTeX citation:

```
@misc{forney2024,  
  author = {Forney, Christian and Stuber, Martin},  
  editor = {Baudry, Jérôme and Burkart, Lucas and Joyeux-Prunel,  
    Béatrice and Kurmann, Eliane and Mähr, Moritz and Natale, Enrico and  
    Sibille, Christiane and Twente, Moritz},  
  title = {Connecting Floras and Herbaria Before 1850 – Challenges and  
    Lessons Learned in Digital History of Biodiversity},  
  date = {2024-08-08},  
  url = {https://digihistch24.github.io/book-of-abstracts/submissions/480/},  
  doi = {10.5281/zenodo.13768615},  
  langid = {en},  
  abstract = {Floras and herbaria are particularly valuable sources both  
    for historical analyses of the collaborative knowledge culture of  
    botany and for research into historical biodiversity. Therefore, the  
    digital representation of this complementary sources should fulfil  
    the requirements of the humanities and natural sciences as well. In  
    this paper, we describe challenges, solutions and lessons learned in  
    this regard as a summary of experiences from multiple projects on  
    the data and edition platform \_hallerNet\_ around the Bernese  
    polymath Albrecht von Haller (1708–1777).}  
}
```


For attribution, please cite this work as:

Forney, Christian, and Martin Stuber. 2024. "Connecting Floras and Herbaria Before 1850 – Challenges and Lessons Learned in Digital History of Biodiversity." Edited by Jérôme Baudry, Lucas Burkart, Béatrice Joyeux-Prunel, Eliane Kurmann, Moritz Mähr, Enrico Natale, Christiane Sibille, and Moritz Twente. *Digital History Switzerland 2024: Book of Abstracts*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13768615> .